

2 Figure S1) **Measuring variability among replicates.** Comparison of the overlap between
3 protein-pathway predictions produced by the model when changing the hyperparameter for
4 Number of Walks (NWs). The NW hyperparameter, indicating how many times the starting node
5 should be sampled, was tested from 10 to 80 with each variation of the changed NW
6 hyperparameter for the random walk process replicated three times. A-B) Box plot of the average
7 percentage overlap for protein-pathway predictions between the three replicates produced for all
8 variations of the hyperparameter used (10-80). Overlap of the predictions produced by the model
9 was compared on a per dark kinase basis and then averaged overall for all dark kinases A)
10 filtered for 0.7 confidence or B) filtered for 0.9 confidence.

11 Supplemental Table 1.xlsx

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13 Supplemental Table 1) **Node Statistics**. Table depicting all node type abundance and average
14 degree (number of edges) for node types within our KG.

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19 Supplemental Table 2.xlsx

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21 Supplemental Table 2) **Protein-Pathway Predictions that Overlap with All NW Replicates**.

22 Table depicting all protein-pathway predictions that overlapped with our 10-80 NW (three
23 replicated each for a total of 24 validation sets) organized by abundance of predictions and
24 clustered by protein.

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29 Supplemental Table 3.xlsx

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31 Supplemental Table 3) **Protein-Pathway Predictions that Overlap with Protein-Protein**

32 **Interactions Provided by the Dark Kinase Knowledgebase**. Table depicting all protein-
33 pathway predictions produced through our model that overlapped with the Reactome enrichment
34 results produced through protein-protein interactions from the Dark Kinase Knowledgebase.
35 Pathway associations for dark kinases.

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40 Supplemental Table 4.xlsx

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42 Supplemental Table 4) **Protein-Pathway Predictions that Overlap with Protein-Protein**

43 **Interactions from Internal Datasets Not Used in Training**. Table depicting all protein-
44 pathway predictions that overlapped with the protein-protein interactions from experimentally
45 validated mass-spectrometry data not used in training. Pathway associations that were connected
46 to dark kinases from RegPattern2Vec's predictions were linked to their associated pathway
47 according to Reactome.

48 Supplemental Data 1.csv

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50 Supplemental Data 1) **Subgraph of Paths analyzed for PRKACB Pathway Prediction.** This
51 file can be used to generate the subgraph highlighted in Fig. 5 through use with Cytoscape
52 program. Columns are labeled according to their input in Cytoscape. The file includes more
53 nodes that were displayed in the figure. More information on how this data was generated can be
54 found in manuscript (Results section 3.4)

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59 Supplemental Data 2.csv

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61 Supplemental Data 2) **Subgraph of Paths analyzed for CDK19 Pathway Prediction.** This file
62 can be used to generate the subgraph highlighted in Fig. 6 through use with Cytoscape program.
63 Columns are labeled according to their input in Cytoscape. The file includes more nodes that
64 were displayed in the figure. More information on how this data was generated can be found in
65 manuscript (Results section 3.5)

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70 Supplemental Data 3.csv

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72 Supplemental Data 3) **Subgraph of Paths analyzed for PSKH2 Pathway Prediction.** This file
73 can be used to generate the subgraph highlighted in Fig. 7 through use with Cytoscape program.
74 Columns are labeled according to their input in Cytoscape. The file includes more nodes that
75 were displayed in the figure. More information on how this data was generated can be found in
76 manuscript (Results section 3.6)

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81 Supplemental Data 4.txt

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83 Supplemental Data 4) **Link to Additional Data Needed for Github and Knowledge Graph**
84 This file has a link to OneDrive or a DOI number that links to the data to be downloaded hosted
85 at Zenodo. (either link provides the same data). File contains following: Knowledge Graph,
86 Example Embedding, UniProt IDs to Gene Names File, Reactome IDs to UniProt ID Mapping
87 File, and Folder Hierarchy Need for Example Code. Upon download, the data is formatted in

88 exact way need to be inserted into the main file for the example code to work. See the GitHub
89 <https://github.com/gravelCompBio/RegPattern2Vec> (DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7541894) for more
90 details.